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Flipped classroom strategy in promoting critical thinking in social science

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Abstract

The research study aimed to assess the effectiveness of a flipped classroom strategy in enhancing the critical thinking skills of grade 12 humanities and social sciences students. Two approaches, pre-class and in-class activities were implemented with 80 students from Recto Memorial National High School. Overall, students had a positive perception of the flipped classroom strategy, and their performance in critical thinking tests was generally good. However, there were areas for improvement, particularly in inference and evaluation skills. The study found no significant difference in recognition and inferencing skills between the pre-class and in-class activities, but there was a significant difference in interpretation and evaluation skills. Recommendations were made for curriculum developers, supervisors, and administrators to enhance teaching methods through training and workshops, focusing on improving students' inference and evaluation skills. The adoption of the flipped classroom approach was encouraged, especially in social sciences, to make class discussions more engaging. Further research with a larger sample size or exploring different critical thinking subskills was suggested to provide more insight into the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom; Pre-class; In-class; Critical thinking

1. Introduction

Education holds significant symbolic importance, representing hope and aspirations for many individuals. For most Filipino families, education is perceived as a crucial step in breaking the cycle of poverty. Alampay and Garcia (2019) noted that Filipino families highly value their children's education, with academic achievements viewed as a means to meet parental expectations and fulfil filial responsibilities. Prior to the changes in the Philippine education curriculum, the country stood as one of merely three nations globally and the sole representative in Asia that adhered to a 10-year basic education system. This posed a consistent disadvantage for Filipino students striving to compete in an ever-expanding global job market (Uyquiengco, 2023). In line with this perspective, the Philippine government, through its education arm, the Department of Education (DepEd), has introduced a new legislation known as the Republic Act 10533 (RA 10533), commonly referred to as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. This law aims to implement the K-12 curriculum, reflecting the government's commitment to enhancing the overall educational system. It is essential that the Philippine education system take action to raise the caliber of graduates it produces.

Moreover, the Department of Education oversees the K-12 education system, which strives to improve students' fundamental skills, create more capable citizens, and get graduates ready for both career and lifetime study (*K-12 Basic Education Curriculum| K12 Philippines*, 2021). The K-12 Basic Education Program is essential for giving the Philippines a competitive edge in the international arena by turning forth graduates who are well-rounded, competent, and flexible and who can make meaningful contributions to society and the global economy. Through expediting the reciprocal recognition of Filipino graduates and professionals abroad, the K-12 program fosters global proficiency. Students can

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select from three tracks in the new curriculum: the Academic, Technical-Vocational-Livelihood, and Sports and Arts strands. Students will also have the chance to participate in immersions, gain meaningful exposure to a range of sectors, and gain experience in the track of their choice. The K–12 curriculum includes more practical applications than the previous curriculum yet offering a more comprehensive and linear curriculum (Enderun Colleges, 2022).

However, despite the efforts of the government and other stake holders, the Philippines still lags in global knowledge index (Banzuelo, 2023). The Philippines' education system faces several, intricate difficulties, such as the digital divide, armed conflict, poverty, and a lack of infrastructure and resources (*Educational Challenges in the Philippines*, n.d.). Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive strategy encompassing increased employment opportunities, enhanced social services, and the promotion of education and skill development. Investing in education infrastructure and offering alternative learning opportunities in conflict-affected areas are essential components of this strategy. Addressing the problems that underlie students' ability to compete globally, as stated as one of the objectives of the K–12 curriculum requires combining instructional strategies for active learning with global issues and weaving them into the existing curriculum. By practicing skill development in the classroom and applying what they have learned to real-world subjects, students can become globally competent. While there is value in memorization, listening to lectures, and reading textbooks, in order to become globally competent, one must combine these learning strategies with more active learning (*Teaching for Global Competence in a Rapidly Changing World*, n.d.).

Staake (2023) defines teaching strategy as the techniques employed by teachers to meet learning goals, highlighting the need for innovative approaches such as the Flipped Classroom Model. In other words, just about any educational action you can imagine is an illustration of an instructional method. They are sometimes referred to as learning and teaching strategies. In the article entitled “The modern teacher of Social Studies” It was demonstrated how dull social studies can become and why a modern social studies instructor is necessary to meet this need (PressReader.com – Digital Newspaper & Magazine Subscriptions, n.d.). Consequently, an innovative teaching strategy is needed such as the Flipped Classroom Model. The Flipped Classroom Model, defined by Ağırman and Ercoşkun (2022), involves learning fundamental components outside of class using technology and engaging in more advanced work during class time. This approach enhances student engagement, learning, and critical thinking skills, addressing the perception of social science as boring and irrelevant (Richardson, 2022). Flipped classroom is designed to increase student's engagement, learning, and critical thinking skills by having learners' complete readings of their lectures at home and work on actual problem-solving during class time. It is crucial to adapt teaching methods to the diverse characteristics of 21st-century learners, emphasizing effective communication, critical thinking, and responsibility (What Is a 21st Century Learner? n.d.).

“Innovation in education means solving a real problem in a new, simple way to promote equitable learning” (*Strengthening Education Systems and Innovation*, n.d.-b). Innovation in education focuses on raising the standard of instruction, putting in place a system that gives children access to school, and enhancing the effectiveness and ease of learning for students. A great innovation in education is flipped classroom model or strategy. Butterfield (2022) noted that flipped classroom model has been in use for more than a decade. Although professors at the University of Miami experimented with the original impetus, known as the inverted classroom, their ideas did not catch on until seven years later when two high school teachers in Colorado learned about it and since then the flipped classroom pedagogy has taken off.

Humanities and Social Sciences is one of the strands offered in the SHS under the Academic Track. Students who plan to major in journalism, communication arts, liberal arts, education, or other social science-related fields in college should enroll in this strand. The focus of the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand is on enhancing a student's reading, writing, and speaking abilities, most students who select HUMSS strand hope to become active participants in society who will interact with a wide range of people (Apolinar, 2021). The strand covers fields that deal with the exploration of human condition using analytical, critical, and empirical ways, thereby studying change in society and human behavior. While critical thinking is defined as the process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information as a basis for belief and action, active engagement on the other hand is the process of engaging all students in activities that encourage them to gain a deeper understanding of the material being presented by working with and reflecting on it. Critical Thinking and engagement are two important skills that a student of social science should possess.

To sum up, the flipped classroom paradigm offers a viable way to teach social science in the twenty-first century while utilizing new technology and meeting students' changing requirements. Through the adoption of an interactive and collaborative online platform in place of traditional lecture-based learning, educators can foster deeper conversations, critical thinking, and conceptual application among students. This cutting-edge teaching approach not only helps students gain a deeper comprehension of social science but also gives them the tools they need to succeed in the classroom by teaching them digital literacy, self-directed learning, and communication. As we negotiate the always

shifting field of education, the flipped classroom model comes to light as a game-changing instrument that equips teachers and students to succeed in the fast-paced 21st century.

Objectives of the Study

The study investigates the effectiveness of the flipped classroom model in social science education, specifically its ability to improve critical thinking skills. By exploring the connection between technology, active learning, and social science teaching, the study aims to provide valuable insights for educators, curriculum designers, and policymakers. Understanding the impact of the flipped classroom on critical thinking in social science is crucial for preparing students for the modern world.

2. Methodology

The study investigates the effectiveness of the flipped classroom model as a teaching strategy for HUMSS specialized subjects. It utilized a quasi-experimental design, focusing on Grade 12 students at Recto Memorial National High School. The independent variable was the flipped classroom model's Pre-class and In-class activities, while the dependent variable was students' performance in critical thinking skills in social sciences. The study aims to explore the perception and effectiveness of the flipped classroom model in promoting critical thinking in social science subjects among HUMSS students. Purposive sampling was used to select 80 participants from two sections handling the specialized subject. This non-probability sampling technique allowed for the intentional selection of participants meeting specific criteria relevant to the research inquiry. While not representative of the entire population, purposive sampling provides rich insights into the selected criteria, enhancing the study's quality. Overall, the study seeks to provide valuable insights into the experiences, perceptions, and academic engagement of Grade 12 HUMSS students regarding the flipped classroom model in social science teaching.

2.1. Research Instrument

The researcher used a survey questionnaire and performance tests to collect data on respondents' perceptions and critical thinking skills regarding the flipped classroom model. The questionnaire focused on pre-class and in-class activities, while the performance tests assessed critical thinking adapted the Watson Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal. The questionnaire underwent verification for content and consistency, and the performance tests were validated by experts before being administered to students. The tests covered topics from the first three weeks of the second semester, specifically in Community Engagement, Solidarity, and Citizenship. A table of specification was created to ensure an even distribution of questions on concepts and perspectives related to community.

2.2. Statistical Treatment

The research study utilized statistical analysis to address the research question. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as weighted mean and standard deviation to examine student perceptions of the flipped classroom model in social science subjects. T-Test was employed to compare test results between pre-class and in-class activities.

3. Results and Discussion

The study's collected data are included in this chapter and are shown in tables and figures along with the interpretations that go with them. The study's conclusions and suggestions were derived from the analysis and interpretation of the data.

Table 1 Perception of Flipped Classroom Strategy in terms of Pre-class activity

Indicator	Mean	St. deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The video lectures provided before class effectively help me understand the upcoming topics	3.46	0.50	Agree
Watching video lectures before class enhances my overall comprehension of the subject matter	3.30	0.46	Agree

The pre-class video lectures motivate me to actively engage with the course content	3.16	0.54	Agree
Pre-class activity such as video lectures help students manage their time more efficient by providing a structured approach to learning outside of the classroom.	3.25	0.61	
I am satisfied with the use of pre-class video lectures in the flipped classroom model.	3.28	0.53	Agree
The assigned pre-class readings significantly contribute to my understanding of the upcoming topics.	3.25	0.58	Agree
Online modules help me grasp complex concepts more effectively than traditional lectures.	2.96	0.68	Agree
Pre-class activities allow me to engage in a more meaningful discussions and activities during in-class session.	3.23	0.48	Agree
Pre-class activities require students to think critically about the material, formulating	3.29	0.53	Agree
I find the online modules engaging and conducive to learning.	3.04	0.56	Agree
Overall	3.22	0.56	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00(Strongly agree) 2.50 – 3.49 (Agree) 1.50 – 2.49 (Disagree) 1.00- 1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 1 displays respondents' positive perception of the flipped classroom strategy in terms of pre-class activities, with an overall mean value of 3.22. The majority agreed that activities such as watching video lectures before class help them better understand the material and prepare for in-depth discussions during class. This supports the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach, as seen in a study by Asad et al. (2022) which found that many students prefer this method over traditional teaching, especially in the context of the pandemic.

Table 2 Perception of Flipped Classroom in terms of In-class activity

Indicator	Mean	St. deviation	Verbal Interpretation
In-class group discussions provide valuable insights and perspectives that I might not have considered on my own	3.24	0.53	Agree
Group discussions are effective way to engage with my peers and the course content	3.41	0.54	Agree
Group discussions improve my ability to communicate my ideas clearly to others.	3.40	0.52	Agree
In-class activities contribute to creating an active and dynamic learning environment	3.31	0.47	Agree
The hands-on nature of in-class activity often makes learning more enjoyable and meaningful, contributing to a positive classroom atmosphere	3.31	0.56	Agree
I find hands-on activities to be an effective way to apply what I've learned in pre-class materials	3.31	0.52	Agree
Collaborative projects in the flipped classroom apply what I've learned in pre-class materials.	3.23	0.53	Agree
Collaborative projects enhance my ability to synthesize information and solve real-world problems	3.26	0.47	Agree

I find hands-on activities and collaborative projects to be engaging and relevant to the course content	3.33	0.52	Agree
In-class activities, such as hands-on tasks and collaborative projects, help me develop practical skills	3.45	0.53	Agree
Overall	3.33	0.52	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00(Strongly agree) 2.50 – 3.49 (Agree) 1.50 – 2.49 (Disagree) 1.00- 1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

The highest mean response in the assessment of respondents' perceptions of the flipped classroom strategy was for indicator ten, scoring 3.45. This indicates that students find in-class activities effective for developing practical skills through hands-on tasks and collaborative projects. On the other hand, collaborative projects in flipped classrooms were rated lowest at 3.23, suggesting that students agreed on the enhancement of learning experiences through group projects. The overall mean score of 3.33 shows that the flipped classroom approach benefits students' critical thinking abilities, as supported by previous studies.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondent's score in Pre-class activity

Score	Recognition		Inferencing		Interpretation		Evaluation		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
9-10	26	32.5	3	3.75	7	8.75	9	11.25	Excellent
7-8	32	40	26	32.5	28	35.0	21	26.25	Very good
5-6	18	22.5	34	42.5	30	37.5	29	36.25	Good
3-4	4	5.0	13	16.25	14	17.5	17	21.25	Fair
0-2	0	0.0	4	5.0	1	1.25	4	5.0	Poor
TOTAL	80	100	80	100.0	80	100	80	100	

Legend: 9 – 10 (Excellent) 7 – 8 (Very Good) 5 – 6 (Good) 3 – 4 (Fair) 0 – 2 (Poor)

Table 3 presents the pre-class activity scores of 80 respondents on critical thinking abilities such as identification, inference, interpretation, and evaluation. 40% of the learners scored in the 7-8 range for recognition, while 5% fell into the 3-4 bracket, and none scored lower than 2. For inference, 42.5% scored in the 5-6 range, with 5 learners scoring below 2. Interpretation results were split between 5-6 and 7-8 ranges, with 37.5% and 35% answering correctly respectively. Evaluation tests showed 36.25% scoring responses as good and 26.25% as very good, while 4 students received poor interpretations and scores lower than 2. The pre-class activity results indicated strong performance in critical thinking, especially in assumption recognition. Inferencing received the lowest scores among the four tests. A study by Ghani in 2019 involving university students found a positive attitude towards inference-making but a lack of corresponding ability in tests. This discrepancy may explain the poor performance of college students in pre-class activities, particularly in inferencing skills. Overall, university EFL learners showed positivity towards drawing conclusions but struggled to demonstrate the corresponding aptitude, highlighting a gap between attitude and skill level.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondent's score in In-class activity

Score	Recognition		Inferencing		Interpretation		Evaluation		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
9-10	34	42.5	5	6.25	22	27.50	23	28.75	Excellent
7-8	20	25.0	22	27.5	26	32.50	21	26.25	Very good
5-6	21	26.25	37	46.25	21	26.25	25	31.25	Good

3-4	4	5.0	14	17.50	10	12.5	7	8.75	Fair
0-2	1	1.25	2	2.50	1	1.25	4	5.0	Poor
TOTAL	80	100	80	100.0	80	100	80	100	

Legend: 9 – 10 (Excellent) 7 – 8 (Very Good) 5 – 6 (Good) 3 – 4 (Fair) 0 – 2 (Poor)

Table illustrates the students' performance on a critical thinking test during in-class activities. The recognition of assumption had the highest score, with 34 out of 80 students scoring in the 9-10 range. Interpretation followed closely, with 48 students scoring in the 7-8 and 9-10 range, comprising 60.2% of the total. Evaluation had 23 students scoring in the 9-10 range, featuring excellent verbal interpretation. Inferencing had the lowest scores, with only five students scoring in the 9-10 range, but 37 learners scoring in the 5-6 range with good verbal interpretation. The results suggest a moderate outcome, especially in inferencing, aligning with previous research by Seventika et al. (2019) and Hidayanti (2016) indicating low sub-skill levels among students.

Table 5 Test of Difference Between Pre-class and In-class Performances

Critical Thinking Skills	Pre-Class		In-Class		t	df	Sig. (2- Tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Recognition	7.54	1.76	7.75	2.01	-1.06	79	0.290
Inferencing	5.79	1.76	5.83	1.68	-0.020	79	0.842
Interpretation	6.19	1.72	7.08	2.05	-5.07	79	0.000
Evaluation	5.80	2.05	6.83	2.25	-4.17	79	0.000

The study analyzed the performance of students on critical thinking assessments in pre-class and in-class activities. The results showed no significant difference in performance related to the recognition sub-skill, with in-class activities scoring slightly higher. Similarly, there was no significant difference in inferencing outcomes between the two activities. However, there was a significant difference in interpretation and evaluation sub-skills, with in-class activities scoring higher.

It was noted that students often struggle with critical thinking exams, as they may possess a vague understanding of the concept but lack understanding of its process. Educators play a crucial role in developing students' critical thinking skills, particularly in social science education. Teaching critical thinking early on can help students analyze societal issues and make informed decisions as future citizens. A study by Muslem et al. emphasized the importance of teachers supporting students in using critical thinking skills, as they are essential for comprehension and analysis. In contrast, Moro et al. found that students may value critical thinking but struggle to develop it in practice, highlighting the need for targeted educational interventions. Overall, critical thinking is key to developing students' cognitive abilities and preparing them for real-world challenges.

4. Conclusion

The study found that respondents had a positive perception of the flipped classroom strategy for both pre-class and in-class activities. While there were varying levels of performance in critical thinking abilities, overall, students performed well in recognizing, inferring, interpreting, and evaluating information. The in-class activity showed good performance in critical thinking tests, particularly in assumption and interpretation recognition, evaluation, and inferencing. There was no significant difference between pre-class and in-class performance in critical thinking tests on sub-skills recognition and inferencing, leading to a failure to reject the null hypothesis. However, there was a significant difference in performance in interpretation and evaluation sub-skills, leading to non-sustainment of the null hypothesis.

Recommendation

The study recommends that curriculum developers, educational supervisors, and school administrators should conduct training and workshops to improve teaching methods, with a focus on enhancing students' critical thinking skills. The use of the flipped classroom approach is encouraged for social science teachers to make class discussions more engaging. Teachers should identify areas where students struggle with inference and evaluation and create targeted

improvement plans. More class time should be allocated to activities that enhance interpretation and evaluation skills, such as group discussions or case studies. Teaching methods should be regularly reviewed and modified based on student feedback. Future research could explore the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach on critical thinking skills and student engagement with a larger sample size.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Appendix A Pre-test

Direction: Encircle the letter of the correct answer from the options given.

- "Community situations vary. Each community has its own context and given realities."
Given the statement above, what can be inferred about the nature of community situations?
 - Communities share identical contexts and realities.
 - The diversity of community situations is influenced by various factors.
 - Context and realities have no impact on community situations.
 - Every community faces identical challenges regardless of its context.
- Community Dynamics is the process of change and development in communities of all living organisms—including plants, microorganisms, and small and large creatures of every sort."
What can be inferred from the given phrase about the scope of Community Dynamics?
 - Community Dynamics only applies to human communities.
 - Community Dynamics excludes microorganisms from its scope.
 - Community Dynamics is limited to the development of large creatures.
 - Community Dynamics encompasses living organisms such as plants, microorganisms, and various creatures.
- "Go to the people - Live with them, learn from them, love them, start with what they know, build with what they have."
What can be inferred about the approach or philosophy suggested by the statement?
 - Isolation and detachment are essential for understanding communities.
 - Building relationships and understanding the community require direct engagement and immersion.
 - People should be left alone to solve their problems without external assistance.
 - Knowledge and resources should be imposed on communities from an external perspective

4-6 - Community situations vary. Each community has its own context and given realities. Those interested in working in the community must first have a clear picture and good grasp of the entity they are trying to address. It is in appreciating the features and elements of community that engagement processes and actions become relevant, acceptable, and appropriate. Without a deep and wide knowledge of one's target community, interventions may emerge as exclusive, inappropriate or totally insensitive to the people."

Question:

Tell whether the assumptions made is TRUE or FALSE based on the information implied in the above statement.

- Without a deep knowledge of a community, engagement processes and actions may risk being irrelevant and unacceptable.
 - TRUE
 - Somewhat TRUE
 - FALSE
 - Somewhat False

5. A lack of understanding about a community may lead to interventions that are insensitive and exclusive.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat False
6. Comprehensive knowledge of a target community is unnecessary as long as the intentions behind interventions are positive.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat False
7. Based on the statement "Go to the people- Live with them, learn from them, love them, start with what they know, build with what they have," what is the implied approach to community engagement and development?
 - A. Isolate from the community, relying solely on theoretical knowledge.
 - B. Engage with the community, immerse oneself in their environment, and collaboratively build upon their existing knowledge and resources.
 - C. Impose predetermined solutions without considering the community's perspectives.
 - D. All of the above

8 – 9 Imagine you are a community engagement coordinator tasked with developing a program to address a specific issue in a community. Your success depends on your understanding of the features and elements of the community. Consider the following scenario and answer the questions that follow:

You have been assigned to a community with diverse cultural backgrounds, socioeconomic statuses, and age groups. The issue you are addressing is related to environmental sustainability. Your goal is to implement initiatives that encourage sustainable practices while respecting the unique characteristics of the community.

8. Illustrate how can a lack of community knowledge impact the success of environmental sustainability initiatives?
 - A. It has no impact.
 - B. It may lead to irrelevant and ineffective interventions.
 - C. It speeds up the implementation process.
 - D. It enhances community participation.
9. Compose the best description of the relationship between community engagement and knowledge of the target community.
 - A. Community engagement becomes relevant, acceptable, and appropriate with community knowledge.
 - B. Community engagement is unnecessary for successful interventions.
 - C. Community engagement is more successful without community knowledge.
 - D. They are unrelated.

10-11 In the vibrant neighbourhood of Maple Grove, a community initiative is launched to enhance local parks and recreational spaces. The project aims to involve residents in decision-making, ensuring the improvements align with the diverse needs and preferences of the community.

As the initiative unfolds, the organizers realize the importance of understanding community dynamics. The neighbourhood consists of families with varying cultural backgrounds, elderly residents who have lived there for decades, and young professionals who recently moved in. Each group has unique perspectives on how the park enhancements should be prioritized.

10. *Based on the given scenario, is it a requirement for a community worker to understand the dynamics of the community when launching a project?*
 - Yes, successful community initiatives require not only addressing physical needs but also recognizing the social fabric that binds the community together.
 - A. Strong Argument.
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
11. To understand community dynamics, should the community worker develop a strategic plan?
 - Yes, to better understand the dynamics, the organizers should conduct surveys, host community meetings, and engage in one-on-one conversations with residents.
 - A. Strong Argument.
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument

institutions, and other settings that influence individuals, groups, and organizations. Community psychology as a science seeks to understand relationships between environmental conditions and the development of health and wellbeing of all members of a community."

Question:

Tell whether the assumptions made is TRUE or FALSE based on the information implied in the above statement.

18. Social issues, social institutions, and environmental settings play a significant role in shaping the behavior and well-being of individuals, groups, and organizations.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
19. The influence of society on individual and community functioning is not a significant aspect of community psychology.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
20. Individual and community functioning are influenced by person-environment interactions and societal factors.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
21. Which of the following statements best captures the essence of diversity?
 - A. A community feels strongly when there is uniformity or when everyone is the same.
 - B. Diverse strategies should be rejected in the interest of uniformity.
 - C. Diversity acknowledges and embraces differences, recognizing their value in creating a richer and more vibrant community.
 - D. The state or attribute of possessing one shape, kind, concept, etc. the condition of having members of a group or organization who share the same racial or cultural backgrounds.
22. Interpret the statement "Populations of an organism will appear in an environment as its requirements for establishment are met." What does this imply about the relationship between organisms and their environment?
 - A. The appearance of organisms in an environment is unrelated to their requirements for establishment.
 - B. Organisms appear randomly in any environment without any correlation to their requirements.
 - C. Populations of organisms are solely determined by the availability of resources in their environment.
 - D. All of the above
23. Elucidate the connection between community and geographical location.
 - A. The geographical area a community occupies has no impact on its shared identity or member interactions.
 - B. There is a fundamental connection between community and territory, where the geographical area influences both physical characteristics and social dynamics.
 - C. The link between community and territory is limited to the physical aspects and does not affect social interactions among members.
 - D. The physical characteristics of a community are solely determined by its social dynamics.
24. What is the primary characteristic of a community viewed as holistic?
 - A) Emphasis on isolated social issues
 - B) focus solely on economic development.
 - C) Prioritization of environmental concerns over other aspects
 - D) Recognition of the interconnectivity of people and place-based strategies
25. Is a community generally defined by a common cultural heritage, language, beliefs, and shared interests?
 - *Yes, the commonality in cultural heritage, language, beliefs, and shared interests forms the basis for defining and understanding the concept of a community.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somewhat Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
26. Is it possible to form a virtual community based on shared interests and interactions online?
 - *No, personal connections and interactions play a crucial role in the establishment of a community.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument

35. Why is local community power considered important?
- A. To centralize decision-making at the national level.
 - B. To ensure equal distribution of resources within the community.
 - C. To limit the capacity for change and maintain stability.
 - D. To empower individuals to influence decisions and drive positive change locally.
36. In what way can coercion become a basis of local community power?
- A. By promoting open and inclusive dialogue.
 - B. Through voluntary collaboration and consensus-building
 - C. By using force or threats to influence decision-making.
 - D. Through transparent and accountable governance practices
37. Does power in numbers constitute a more local power?
- *Yes, the phrase "power in numbers" suggests that a larger group of individuals has the potential to wield more influence or power collectively, and this concept can extend to local contexts.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
- 38-39** In the town of Tikob, a contentious debate arises over the construction of a new waste management facility. The local government strongly supports the project, citing economic benefits and job opportunities, while a significant portion of the community is vehemently opposed, concerned about environmental impact and potential health hazards.
38. The local government begins subtly pressuring vocal opponents of the waste management facility. Residents who express dissent are facing job insecurities, threats, and intimidation. Is this an example of coercion and intimidation as the basis of power?
- *No, it is an example of a legitimate power vested in the local government to make decisions on behalf of the people.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
39. Tikob community leaders, initially against the project, are now showing signs of support after facing subtle coercion. Are these an example of an ethical dilemma about local power dynamics?
- *Yes, community leaders had to deal with how to avoid pressure while yet upholding their moral standards.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
40. You have recently moved to a small, close-knit town for a job opportunity. The community has its unique behavioral patterns and cultural norms. You are keen on assimilating into your new environment, understanding the importance of embracing the community's way of life. Over time, you observe and adopt certain behavioral patterns that are characteristic of the local culture.
- *The scenario portrayed an isolated scene which normally do not happen in real life since someone's culture cannot be transferred or learned over time, it is innate with them.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument

Appendix B Post-test

Direction: Encircle the letter of the correct answer from the options given.

1. Why is a community regarded as a social system?

- A. Because communities primarily focus on individual interests.
 - B. Because communities' function in isolation from broader social structures.
 - C. Since social systems exclude the role of individuals in community development.
 - A. Due to the interconnectedness and interdependence of individuals within the community.
2. What can be inferred about the characterization of community when it is described as monolithic?
- A. Every community is exactly the same in terms of structure and dynamics.
 - B. Community is portrayed as having diverse and varied characteristics.
 - C. The term "monolithic" suggests that communities are static and unchanging.
 - D. There is a recognition of the complexity and diversity within communities.
3. "A community can also be defined by describing the social and political networks that link individuals, community organizations, and leaders. Understanding these networks is critical to planning efforts in engagement."
What inference can be drawn about the significance of social and political networks in defining and planning for a community?
- A. Social and political networks have no impact on defining a community.
 - B. Understanding these networks is considered irrelevant for community engagement planning.
 - C. The definition of a community is influenced by the connections among individuals, community organizations, and leaders.
 - D. Planning efforts in engagement should solely focus on individual perspectives within a community.

4. Community Dynamics is the process of change, growth, and development in communities involving all of its members."

Question:

What can be inferred about the inclusivity of community members in the process of change, growth, and development based on the statement?

- A. Community members play a passive role in the process of change and development.
- B. The mentioned process actively engages and includes all members of the community.
- C. The process of change and development primarily focuses on a select group within the community.
- D. Change, growth, and development in communities exclude the involvement of community members.

5- 7. "Community psychology is the branch of psychology concerned with person-environment interactions and the ways society affects individual and community functioning. Community psychology focuses on social issues, social institutions, and other settings that influence individuals, groups, and organizations. Community psychology as a science seeks to understand relationships between environmental conditions and the development of health and wellbeing of all members of a community."

Tell whether the assumptions made is TRUE or FALSE based on the information implied in the above statement.

- 5. Social issues, social institutions, and environmental settings play a significant role in shaping the behavior and well-being of individuals, groups, and organizations.
 - C. TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
- 6. The influence of society on individual and community functioning is not a significant aspect of community psychology.
 - C. TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
- 7. Individual and community functioning are influenced by person-environment interactions and societal factors.
 - C. TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE

8. Which of the following statements best captures the essence of diversity?
- A. A community feels strongly when there is uniformity or when everyone is the same.
 - B. Diverse strategies should be rejected in the interest of uniformity.
 - C. Diversity acknowledges and embraces differences, recognizing their value in creating a richer and more vibrant community.
 - D. The state or attribute of possessing one shape, kind, concept, etc. the condition of having members of a group or organization who share the same racial or cultural backgrounds.
9. Interpret the statement "Populations of an organism will appear in an environment as its requirements for establishment are met." What does this imply about the relationship between organisms and their environment?
- A. The appearance of organisms in an environment is unrelated to their requirements for establishment.
 - B. Organisms appear randomly in any environment without any correlation to their requirements.
 - C. Populations of organisms are solely determined by the availability of resources in their environment.
 - D. All of the above
10. Elucidate the connection between community and geographical location.
- E. The geographical area a community occupies has no impact on its shared identity or member interactions.
 - A. There is a fundamental connection between community and territory, where the geographical area influences both physical characteristics and social dynamics.
 - B. The link between community and territory is limited to the physical aspects and does not affect social interactions among members.
 - C. The physical characteristics of a community are solely determined by its social dynamics.
11. What is the primary characteristic of a community viewed as holistic?
- A) Emphasis on isolated social issues
 - B) focus solely on economic development.
 - C) Prioritization of environmental concerns over other aspects
 - D) Recognition of the interconnectivity of people and place-based strategies
12. Is a community generally defined by a common cultural heritage, language, beliefs, and shared interests?
- *Yes, the commonality in cultural heritage, language, beliefs, and shared interests forms the basis for defining and understanding the concept of a community.*
 - C. Strong Argument
 - D. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
13. Is it possible to form a virtual community based on shared interests and interactions online?
- *No, personal connections and interactions play a crucial role in the establishment of a community.*
 - C. Strong Argument
 - D. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
14. "A community has fuzzy boundaries." What inference can be made regarding the nature of boundaries in a community based on the statement?
- A. Community boundaries are precisely defined and clear-cut.
 - B. Community boundaries are undefined and lack clarity.
 - C. Fuzzy boundaries have no impact on the concept of community.
 - D. Boundaries in a community are static and unchanging.
15. One basis of local power is the Capacity to create linkages and develop helpful relationships with powerful individuals, family, and organization. What basis of local power can you infer from the statement?
- E. Connections
 - F. Coercion
 - G. Personal Traits
 - H. Legitimate power
16. "Social change is characterized by alterations of cultural attitudes and values, behavior, and social organizations. It is brought about by natural, cultural, religious, political, and economic forces."
Question:
What can be inferred about the factors influencing social change based on the provided statement?
- A. Social change is solely influenced by natural forces.

- B. Cultural attitudes and values have no impact on the process of social change.
- C. The alteration of social organizations is the primary driver of social change.
- D. Social change results from a complex interplay of natural, cultural, religious, political, and economic forces.

17-20. "Not only is the concept of a community a 'construct' (model), but it is also a 'sociological construct.' It is a set of interactions, human behaviors that have meaning and expectations between its members. Not just action, but actions based on shared expectations, values, beliefs, and meanings between individuals."

Question:

Tell whether the assumptions made is TRUE or FALSE based on the information implied in the above statement.

17. The term "sociological construct" suggests that the concept of a community is irrelevant to the field of sociology.
 - C. TRUE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
18. Actions within a community are solely based on individual expectations and values without shared meanings.
 - C. TRUE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
19. Interactions within a community involve human behaviors with shared meaning and expectations among its members.
 - C. TRUE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
20. Shared expectations, values, beliefs, and meanings are integral components of actions within a community.
 - C. TRUE
 - D. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat FALSE
21. What is the primary focus of the concept of community power structure?
 - A. Distribution of power within a local community
 - B. Global economic disparities
 - C. Individual empowerment programs
 - D. Environmental sustainability initiatives
22. Why is local community power considered important?
 - A. To centralize decision-making at the national level.
 - B. To ensure equal distribution of resources within the community.
 - C. To limit the capacity for change and maintain stability.
 - D. To empower individuals to influence decisions and drive positive change locally.
23. In what way can coercion become a basis of local community power?
 - A. By promoting open and inclusive dialogue.
 - B. Through voluntary collaboration and consensus-building
 - C. By using force or threats to influence decision-making.
 - D. Through transparent and accountable governance practices
24. Does power in numbers constitute a more local power?
 - *Yes, the phrase "power in numbers" suggests that a larger group of individuals has the potential to wield more influence or power collectively, and this concept can extend to local contexts.*
 - A. Strong Argument
 - B. Somewhat Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument

25-26. In the town of Tikob, a contentious debate arises over the construction of a new waste management facility. The local government strongly supports the project, citing economic benefits and job opportunities, while a significant portion of the community is vehemently opposed, concerned about environmental impact and potential health hazards.

25. The local government begins subtly pressuring vocal opponents of the waste management facility. Residents who express dissent are facing job insecurities, threats, and intimidation. Is this an example of coercion and intimidation as the basis of power?

➤ *No, it is an example of a legitimate power vested in the local government to make decisions on behalf of the people.*

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------|
| A. Strong Argument | C. Somehow Weak Argument |
| B. Somehow Strong Argument | D. Weak Argument |

26. Tikob community leaders, initially against the project, are now showing signs of support after facing subtle coercion. Are these an example of an ethical dilemma about local power dynamics?

➤ *Yes, community leaders had to deal with how to avoid pressure while yet upholding their moral standards.*

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------|
| A. Strong Argument | C. Somehow Weak Argument |
| B. Somehow Strong Argument | D. Weak Argument |

27. You have recently moved to a small, close-knit town for a job opportunity. The community has its unique behavioral patterns and cultural norms. You are keen on assimilating into your new environment, understanding the importance of embracing the community's way of life. Over time, you observe and adopt certain behavioral patterns that are characteristic of the local culture.

➤ *The scenario portrayed an isolated scene which normally do not happen in real life since someone's culture cannot be transferred or learned over time, it is innate with them.*

- | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------|
| A. Strong Argument | C. Somehow Weak Argument |
| B. Somehow Strong Argument | D. Weak Argument |

28. "Community situations vary. Each community has its own context and given realities."

Given the statement above, what can be inferred about the nature of community situations?

- A) Communities share identical contexts and realities.
- B) The diversity of community situations is influenced by various factors.
- C) Context and realities have no impact on community situations.
- D) Every community faces identical challenges regardless of its context.

29. Community Dynamics is the process of change and development in communities of all living organisms—including plants, microorganisms, and small and large creatures of every sort."

What can be inferred from the given phrase about the scope of Community Dynamics?

- A) Community Dynamics only applies to human communities.
- B) Community Dynamics excludes microorganisms from its scope.
- C) Community Dynamics is limited to the development of large creatures.
- D) Community Dynamics encompasses living organisms such as plants, microorganisms, and various creatures.

30. "Go to the people - Live with them, learn from them, love them, start with what they know, build with what they have."

What can be inferred about the approach or philosophy suggested by the statement?

- A) Isolation and detachment are essential for understanding communities.
- B) Building relationships and understanding the community require direct engagement and immersion.
- C) People should be left alone to solve their problems without external assistance.
- D) Knowledge and resources should be imposed on communities from an external perspective.

31-33. Community situations vary. Each community has its own context and given realities. Those interested in working in the community must first have a clear picture and good grasp of the entity they are trying to address. It is in appreciating the features and elements of community that engagement processes and actions become relevant,

acceptable, and appropriate. Without a deep and wide knowledge of one's target community, interventions may emerge as exclusive, inappropriate or totally insensitive to the people."

Question:

Tell whether the assumptions made is TRUE or FALSE based on the information implied in the above statement.

31. Without a deep knowledge of a community, engagement processes and actions may risk being irrelevant and unacceptable.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat False
32. A lack of understanding about a community may lead to interventions that are insensitive and exclusive.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat False
33. Comprehensive knowledge of a target community is unnecessary as long as the intentions behind interventions are positive.
 - A. TRUE
 - B. Somewhat TRUE
 - C. FALSE
 - D. Somewhat False
34. Based on the statement "Go to the people- Live with them, learn from them, love them, start with what they know, build with what they have," what is the implied approach to community engagement and development?
 - A. Isolate from the community, relying solely on theoretical knowledge.
 - B. Engage with the community, immerse oneself in their environment, and collaboratively build upon their existing knowledge and resources.
 - C. Impose predetermined solutions without considering the community's perspectives.
 - D. All of the above
35. Illustrate how can a lack of community knowledge impact the success of environmental sustainability initiatives?
 - A. It has no impact.
 - B. It may lead to irrelevant and ineffective interventions.
 - C. It speeds up the implementation process.
 - D. It enhances community participation.
36. Compose the best description of the relationship between community engagement and knowledge of the target community.
 - A. Community engagement becomes relevant, acceptable, and appropriate with community knowledge.
 - B. Community engagement is unnecessary for successful interventions.
 - C. Community engagement is more successful without community knowledge.
 - D. They are unrelated.

37-38. In the vibrant neighbourhood of Maple Grove, a community initiative is launched to enhance local parks and recreational spaces. The project aims to involve residents in decision-making, ensuring the improvements align with the diverse needs and preferences of the community.

As the initiative unfolds, the organizers realize the importance of understanding community dynamics. The neighbourhood consists of families with varying cultural backgrounds, elderly residents who have lived there for decades, and young professionals who recently moved in. Each group has unique perspectives on how the park enhancements should be prioritized.

37. *Based on the given scenario, is it a requirement for a community worker to understand the dynamics of the community when launching a project?*
 - Yes, successful community initiatives require not only addressing physical needs but also recognizing the social fabric that binds the community together.
 - A. Strong Argument.
 - B. Somehow Strong Argument
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument
 - D. Weak Argument
38. To understand community dynamics, should the community worker develop a strategic plan?
 - Yes, to better understand the dynamics, the organizers should conduct surveys, host community meetings, and engage in one-on-one conversations with residents.
 - A. Strong Argument.
 - C. Somehow Weak Argument

- B. Somehow Strong Argument D. Weak Argument
39. Imagine you are a community organizer working in a diverse neighborhood. Different cultural, social, and economic groups reside in the area. One day, you notice a growing tension between two cultural communities regarding the use of a shared public space. Each group has its own set of needs and preferences for the use of the space. As a community organizer, you recognize the importance of understanding community dynamics. Given the scenario, how might an understanding of community dynamics benefit you in addressing the tension and finding a solution to the conflict over the shared public space?
- By recognizing and respecting the cultural, social, and economic factors influencing the conflict
- A. Strong Argument. C. Somehow Weak Argument
- B. Somehow Strong Argument D. Weak Argument
40. As a community organizer facing tension between two cultural communities over the use of a shared public space, what will you do to solve the conflict?
- I will push through with my project plan and ignore the conflict, anyway the project will benefit all sectors of the target community including those different groups.
- A. Strong Argument. C. Somehow Weak Argument
- B. Somehow Strong Argument D. Weak Argument

Appendix C Survey Questionnaire

Students Survey Questionnaire

FLIPPED CLASSROOM STRATEGY IN PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING IN SOCIAL SCIENCE

Name(optional); _____

Direction: Please indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with each of these statements regarding Flipped classroom Model as it promotes critical thinking in the context of social science teaching.

Perception towards Flipped Classroom Model

What impression do you have of the flipped classroom model in terms of:

- **Pre-class Activity**

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The video lectures provided before class effectively help me understand the upcoming topics.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Watching video lectures before class enhances my overall comprehension of the subject matter.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The pre-class video lectures motivate me to actively engage with the course content.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pre-class activity such as video lectures help students manage their time more efficient by providing a structured approach to learning outside of the classroom.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the use of pre-class video lectures in the flipped classroom model.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The assigned pre-class readings significantly contribute to my understanding of the upcoming topics.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Online modules help me grasp complex concepts more effectively than traditional lectures.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Pre-class activities allow me to engage in a more meaningful discussions and activities during in-class session.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pre-class activities require students to think critically about the material, formulating questions and preparing for discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I find the online modules engaging and conducive to learning.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

In-class Activity

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
In-class group discussions provide valuable insights and perspectives that I might not have considered on my own.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Group discussions are effective way to engage with my peers and the course content.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Group discussions improve my ability to communicate my ideas clearly to others.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In-class activities contribute to creating an active and dynamic learning environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The hands-on nature of in-class activity often makes learning more enjoyable and meaningful, contributing to a positive classroom atmosphere.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I find hands-on activities to be an effective way to apply what I've learned in pre-class materials.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Collaborative projects in the flipped classroom contribute significantly to my learning experience.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Collaborative projects enhance my ability to synthesize information and solve real-world problems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I find hands-on activities and collaborative projects to be engaging and relevant to the course content.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In-class activities, such as hands-on tasks and collaborative projects, help me develop practical skills.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>